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Report on **Milestone 20**

Selection of SSH metadata standards for mapping to SSHOCro

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Abstract: (Text, no more than 2-3 sentences)

This report describes the action plan devised in the context of D4.19 "Mapping of two indicative selected standards to the SSHOCro" and the steps taken to achieve it up to. D4.19 focuses on testing information integration and harmonization by mapping selected metadata from metadata standards used in the Social Sciences and Humanities to the SSHOC Reference Ontology. MS20 report describes the actions undertaken in the selection of the metadata standards process, expands on what informed the decisions regarding the standards selected and offers an outline of the activities planned in the context of D4.19

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1. Introduction

The SSHOC Reference Ontology (SSHOCro) proposes an ontological model and RDF Schema to be used as a top-level ontology for organizing knowledge and information found distributed across various primary sources of information in the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC). It aims at providing a semantic interoperability framework for the description of the SSHOC data life cycle.

SSHOCro will have the function of providing a conceptual model that can be used in order to (re)describe, at a generic level, the real-world life-cycle of creating, using and finding data –amongst other actions –as it actually takes place in the various domains of social sciences and humanities. The practical use of such a conceptual model to the research community is twofold. It can be applied as a standard to devise and implement metadata capture schemes for tracking the data life-cycle in individual projects/institutions/disciplines.

Furthermore, encoded in a semantic data format (e.g. RDF), it can be of use for mapping, transforming and integrating existing data across projects/institutions/disciplines into interoperable pools of information for re-use and further exploitation. Information integration and harmonization is to be tested by mapping selected metadata from (at least) two indicative SSH metadata standards to the common SSHOCro schema.

In what follows, there will be explicit reference to the process of selecting said metadata standards & samples to be mapped to SSHOCro.

2. Description of the Milestone

The process of selecting the metadata standards to be mapped to SSHOCro, was to a large extent guided by the “Report on SSHOC (meta)data interoperability problems” (Broeder et al., 2019) and the work undertaken by SSHIC Task 3.5 *Data and Metadata Interoperability Hub* of SSHOC. The criterion that informed the selection was which metadata standards were deemed “the two most important ones” among scholars using them in their research.

According to Broeder et al. (2019, p. 14), with the exception of DublinCore, which is used by all research communities making up SSHOC, there appears to be a direct correlation between the metadata standards one uses in their research and the scientific domain that their research focuses on (institutional conformity also having something to contribute to the overall decision).

As such, scholars & Research Infrastructures reported using:

- DDI Codebook, DDI Lifecycle, DataCite and Dublin Core for research in Social Sciences;
- TEI, CIDOC-CRM & Dublin Core for research in the Arts and Humanities;
- CMDI, TEI, Dublin Core & OLAC for Language oriented research; and
- EDM & Dublin Core for Cultural Heritage research.

Given the following considerations:

- (i) the standards/metadata schemes regarded pivotal for the research communities/infrastructures making up SSHOC (CESSDA and CLARIN).
- (ii) the trade-off between flexibility and expressivity on the one hand versus difficulty of use on the other
- (iii) the frequency of use, measured by rounded number of records (ibid. p.24-5)
- (iv) the drawbacks mentioned by the scholars approached in the context of interviews carried out by T3.5 –complexity (DDI & CMDI) and proliferation of profiles (for CMDI).

the metadata standards selected to be mapped to SSHOCro were the DDI (Codebook) and CMDI. Besides DDI Codebook and CMDI, the OpenAIRE Research Graph Data Model (Manghi et al., 2017) will also be considered, to ensure interoperability with the SSHOC Marketplace.

DDI

The DDI is a metadata specification for describing social and behavioural science data and data in related domains.¹ It is, in essence, a way of formatting the documentation for a social science data file. It is used to document datasets and allow search in many social science data archives around the world. DDI focuses on both microdata and aggregated data. It has its strength in microdata – data on the characteristics of units of a population, such as individuals or households, collected by a census or a survey for example (Martinez, 2008).

The DDI has emerged as a de facto standard for documenting data in the social and behavioural sciences across the full life cycle. DDI actually has two specifications; the original DDI (versions 1.0-2.5, now called DDI-Codebook) and the life-cycle based DDI (versions 3.0-3.3, now called DDI-Lifecycle). Both are able to describe microdata sets, with a wealth of related metadata (questions, variables, concepts, categories, codes, etc.) (Arofan 2011).

DDI Codebook² enables the generation of thorough documentation that reflects the content of a traditional social science codebook. In that sense, it primarily focuses on bibliographic information about an individual data set and the structure of its variables. Differently put, the distinction among the steps of the data lifecycle is not documented explicitly, but any mention to the process of the data collection/variables manipulation for instance is treated as static, from the perspective of the archive. The DDI Codebook files examined thus far confirm this point of critique, which suggests that the mapping to SSHOCro should take into account records in DDI Lifecycle as well, given that the latter proposes a workflow model (Vardigan 2013).

However, the fact that the vast majority of DDI records are encoded in DDI Codebook, meant that to be of use to the social sciences community, SSHOCro should be interoperable with the standard that is actually in use. Hence, the DDI Codebook files studied thus far were all retrieved from the Ethnic Minority Migration (EMM) Survey Registry,³ Dataverse (Norway),⁴ and the Finnish Social Science Data Archive (FSD) Data Catalogue.⁵ Records from the first two repositories are encoded in DDI Codebook 2.5, whereas the latter in 2.0. The update

¹ DDI specification: <https://ddialliance.org/explore-documentation> [10.06.2020]

² DDI Codebook: <https://ddialliance.org/Specification/DDI-Codebook/2.5/> [10.06.2020]

³ The Ethnic and Migrant Minority (EMM) Survey Registry is a free online tool that allows users to search for and learn about existing quantitative surveys to EMM populations through the compiled survey-level metadata. For more information: <https://ethmigsurveydatahub.eu/emmregistry/> [10.06.2020]

⁴ DataverseNO (<https://dataverse.no/>) is a national, generic repository for open research data from researchers from Norwegian research institutions. [10.06.2020]

⁵ Aila Data Service: https://services.fsd.uta.fi/catalogue/index?lang=en&study_language=en [10.06.2020]

to version 2.5 does not result in interoperability problems between versions in the sample of DDI-XML records that have been studied thus far.

CMDI

The Component MetaData Infrastructure (CMDI) has been initiated by CLARIN as a unified approach to metadata descriptions for Language Resources. Description building blocks, “components”, group together metadata elements that belong together and can potentially be reused in a different context. Components can also group other components. Existing components can be reused as they are, or be adapted by modifying/adding/removing metadata elements/components. Completely new components can be created to model unique aspects of any given language resource. The components necessary to describe a specific type of resource are combined into a profile (Durco & Windhouwer, 2013). Both components and profiles are stored and shared with other users in the CMDI Component Registry⁶ to promote reuse. Each metadata record is expressed as an XML file, including a link to the profile on which it is based.

The form of a profile depends on what is deemed the proper description given (i) a language resource type, (ii) the context of the project it stemmed from or (iii) the repository that it will be stored in.

Consequently, CMDI offers a great degree of flexibility, i.e. a large set of concepts/elements that serve to create profiles, with potentially very little overlap among them. However, this can result in metadata descriptions that are incomparable in terms of content, as well as a proliferation of profiles (Broeder et al.; 2019).

To overcome this problem, only partial mappings from CMDI to SSHOCro will be performed, which take into account a set of CMDI records adhering to the `clarin.eu:cr1:p_1403526079380` profile/schema, i.e. the one used for LINDAT/CLARIN repository resources.⁷ In its turn, this profile encapsulates a core set of metadata components that will serve as the basis for the DDI-CMDI conversion –one of the actions to be undertaken by SSHOC T3.5. If the minimal metadata captured by the said profile are judged adequate for the DDI-CMDI conversion, they could also be used for mappings with the SSHOCro.

⁶ CMDI Component Registry: <https://catalog.clarin.eu/ds/ComponentRegistry/#/> [10.06.2020]

⁷ The definition of the LINDAT_CLARIN profile/schema can be found on the CMDI component registry: https://catalog.clarin.eu/ds/ComponentRegistry#/?itemId=clarin.eu%3Acr1%3Ap_1403526079380®istrySpace=public [10.06.2020]

OpenAIRE

The OpenAIRE Research Graph has been conceived as a resource for researchers, funders, organizations, research communities, SMEs, and publishers to achieve the population and maintenance of the Global Open Science Graph as a complete, trusted, open, public good. This data model is inspired by several existing metadata standards and models such as CERIF.

It includes metadata and links between scientific products. OpenAire proposes two kinds of research results: publications and datasets such as patents, experimental data, software, and all kinds of research outputs. The main entities are research results, persons, organizations, funders, funding streams, projects, communities, facilities, services and (provenance) data sources in support of the free flow, access, sharing, and re-use of research outcomes.

OpenAIRE entity instances are created out of data collected from various data sources of different kinds, such as publication repositories, dataset archives, CRIS systems, etc. Data sources export information packages that may contain information on one or more of such entities and possibly relationships between them. It is important, once each piece of information is extracted from such packages and inserted into the information space as an entity, for such pieces to keep provenance information relative to the originating data source.

It is a powerful schema for transformation of metadata, and it will be used as the aggregation component of MP model. Mappings from OpenAIRE to MP and to SSHOCro will be taken into account for interoperability purposes.

2.1 Role of the Milestone

The achievement of MS20 aims at reporting the activities planned and/or undertaken in the context of SSHOC D4.19 “Mapping of two indicative selected standards to the SSHOCro”. Furthermore, it aims to verify that SSHOCro can in fact provide a semantic interoperability framework for the description of the SSHOC data-lifecycle, by means of offering a conceptual model that can be used to (re)describe the real-world lifecycle as it actually takes place in the various domains of Social Sciences and Humanities at a generic level. That SSHOCro succeeds to capture the actions that are relevant for Social Sciences and Humanities will be confirmed through the mappings of metadata schemas used across said domains to SSHOCro. This process will help resolve any discrepancies between SSHOCro and the relevant metadata standards.

2.2 Means of verification

According its description in the GA, MS20 involves offering an account regarding the process by means of which the metadata standards to be mapped to SSHOCro were selected. The selection process was informed by:

- (a) an extensive literature review on metadata standards used by the SSHOC communities,

(b) a careful consideration of SSHOC deliverables upon publication,

(c) a thorough search on online resources/repositories for metadata records adhering to their respective metadata schemas.

3. Conclusions and next steps

MS20 serves as a steppingstone to the achievement of D4.19 "Mapping of two indicative selected standards to the SSHOCro".

In the next months, the retrieving and analyzing records and data from dedicated SSH repositories, such as FSD Data Catalogue, DataverseNO, EMM Survey Registry and LINDAT/CLARIAH-cz Repository, will be continued.

Selected examples will be mapped to SSHOCro using the X3ML toolkit –developed by FORTH, in order to show how the SSHOCro can be used by the SSH communities. Besides the mapping process is expected to serve as a means to update SSHOCro.

Points of departure from MS20 would be that the mapping to SSHOCro could also take into consideration (a) records in DDI Lifecycle (v3.0-3.3), given that the latter proposes a workflow model that captures the distinct stages in the data lifecycle (b) records from any other SSH local/national repositories of SSHOC partners if suitable examples are found.

References

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List of abbreviations

CERIF	Common European Research Information Format
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
CMDI	Component MetaData Infrastructure
D4.19	Deliverable 4.19
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
EMM	Ethnic and Migrant Minority
EMM Survey Registry	Ethnic and Migrant Minority Survey Registry
FORTH	Foundation for Research and Technology -Hellas
FSD	Finnish Social Science Data Archive
LINDAT/CLARIAH-Cz	Digital Research Infrastructure for Language Technologies, Arts and Humanities
MS20	Milestone 20
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SND	Swedish National Data Service
SSHOC	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud
SSHOCro	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud -Reference Ontology
XML	Extensible Markup Language